

1 **06.06.2025, Sorbonne**

2 **Interviewee: Yadvinder Rana**

3 **Interviewers: Filippo Martini & Francesco Cruz Torres**

4 **S01:** We are here with Yadvinder, Yadvinder Rana, maybe I'll let you
5 introduce yourself independently, you are certainly the best person who
6 can
do it.

7 **S00:** I am a mechanical engineer who worked for many years at Fiat, I
8 worked
9 around the world, I worked for many years at Azimut Benetti, which is the
10 leader in luxury yachts, I was the commercial director for all of Asia, so
11 I lived in Shanghai, Dubai, Mumbai, then I returned and started teaching
12 intercultural negotiation, I have a research doctorate in complex M&A
negotiations and today I dedicate myself to AI and negotiation.

13 **S01:** Very interesting, your path is also very interesting in my opinion for
14 the DBA part that joins the corporate negotiation and engineering part,
15 therefore it still gives a solid, scientific background, it is more
16 quantitative and then it adds the part, and it's a bit more connecting in
17 my opinion in the field...

18 **S00:** //S00: **Negotiating.**

19 **S01:** Yes, in the field of a social science.

20 **S01:** // Exactly. In this you share a bit of the path with Francesco because
21 he is also an engineer.

22 **S00:** Yes, yes, yes, energy engineer.

23 **S01:** Exactly.

24 **S00:** You are a serious engineer.

25 **S01:** Uh, having said that, if it's okay with you to enter the field
26 directly, and I would ask you, you have already told us a little bit about
27 what you do, and I would ask you about your part where you teach
28 negotiation, how you carry it out and what you are doing at the Catholic
29 University?

30 **S00:** So, I teach a module on intercultural negotiation where there are two
31 of us; we combine the part of cultural dimensions, therefore
32 interculturality, with the part of negotiation and then we combine them
33 together with case studies, for example the Tata Ford one that I presented
34 today, so some M&A, cross-border and everything else. One thing we are

35 having the students do is create chatbots that serve as assistants for
36 international negotiations. Theoretically, the task is to create chatbots
37 based on all the knowledge they acquire during the course, which allows
38 them to create chatbots that are assistants for international managers who
39 go to negotiate with clients or suppliers around the world. So we are
40 integrating AI a little bit, and the results last year were excellent, it
41 was the first year we did it, this year we'll see, some have seen an
42 evolution, last year it was very custom GPT, today others are dedicating
43 themselves to other platforms. So very interesting.

44 **S01:** Ah, very interesting, so I imagine that it is an evolving work, in the
45 sense that since the underlying technology evolves, then also the
46 capabilities of those who propose it evolve and gradually it will become
47 more and more interesting

48 **S00:** And not only that, if you remember this morning's panel, when we
49 said
50 that most of the students don't know how to use it, this still forces them
51 to have to use models, prompting and all the rest that are a bit more
52 serious, because otherwise, they won't succeed. So this, yes, forces them a
bit.

53 **S01:** Uh, it's a bit of the discussion we had when we had that chat, it's a
54 fact that sometimes it's not just explaining to them how to do it, but also
55 the fact that they have to start using it. Otherwise, they return to the
56 old patterns and forget it, I leave a part.

57 **S00:** I totally agree. This project is a little ahead of them, but since
58 they do it in a group, it is very interesting because maybe they have
59 someone a bit more technological, they bring them in, others who bring
more
60 competence, others who tell them how to do it, so it turns out very, very
61 well, it's very, very interesting. Let's see how it goes this year. We will
62 see in mid-June now, soon.

63 **S01:** Well then, the second question we have for you is a slightly more
64 political question regarding Europe and the changes that are unfolding and
65 that we are seeing, and political, economic, social transformations,
66 obviously also linked to the migratory aspect, and therefore climate
67 pressure. There are a series of important themes that are obviously setting
68 the agenda somewhat, even in opposition to that method. So, in your field,
69 therefore in the field of negotiation, also in the field of corporate
70 training, and generally in everything you do, how do you see these
changes?

71 What impact do these changes have on your environment?

72 **S00:** What I follow most closely, strictly from a work perspective, is the
73 economic aspect. And what impacts Europe the most in how it proceeds,
the
74 various countries within it, is political instability, which then
75 encompasses all these topics you spoke about. But if you look at Italy,

..1.1. Geopolitical

..1.2. Social

76 paradoxically, which historically has always been an unstable country,
77 right? With governments lasting on average a year and a few months, it has
78 found a bit more political stability. And mine is absolutely not a
79 political judgment, it is simply a fact. Countries that are much more
80 politically stable are completely in disarray. The UK, which has changed
81 prime ministers like socks. Macron himself is struggling to form a
82 coalition with a prime minister. The Germans themselves. So this is a very
83 interesting factor, which clearly has causes that are those you mentioned.
84 Think about immigration, think about social issues, about all the social
85 dynamics happening today, both in France and Germany, with the right
86 rising significantly. However, this leads to a great deal of political instability.
87 This leads to fewer reforms, less stability, and less willingness for
88 investors to invest. Right now, it is a very important factor to consider.
89 We must cheer for slightly longer-lasting governments.

90 **S01:** Especially in Italy, where for decades we have had a very rapid
91 rotation.

92 **S00:** It took a woman to make things work harder. Yes, regardless, exactly.

93 **S01:** Regardless of the qualitative aspect, but only from the descriptive
94 point of view.

95 **S00:** I disagree with Meloni on a thousand things. From an economic point
96 of view, it is extremely important.

97 **S01:** What are the economic challenges that are determined by the issues
98 we discussed earlier?

..3.1.1. Challenges

..5.1. Essential Skill:

..3.1.1. Challenges

99 **S00:** I think what changes a lot today is that **we no longer know what to**
100 **expect from the other side.** It is much more difficult today, in a climate,
101 in this context of uncertainty, to clearly understand what the interests of
102 the other side might be, the alternatives, hence applying negotiation
103 theory, because the world is changing very quickly. **Therefore, being so**
104 **dynamic, we must continually review all our evaluations.** This, in my
105 opinion, we as human beings are not used to, and especially negotiators are
106 not used to it. This applies to all areas, I think the political one, I
107 think the economic one, I think **corporations really struggle. A lot of**
108 **struggle.**

109 **S01:** So let's say the negotiator is caught a bit off guard, because they
110 prepare, they prepare, (one of the great mantras is "prepare, prepare,
111 prepare"), but then they have to keep up, which is difficult, as far as I
112 understand.

..5.3. Teaching Method

113 **S00:** In one of the roleplays I have them do, I make them write down their
114 objectives. And what do they do in negotiation? They remain anchored to

..5.3. Teaching Met 115
 ..5.1. Essential Skill: 116
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those objectives even when they have different information. This is even more relevant today when things are changing so quickly. Objectives must certainly be set. You must prepare, but be flexible. **Write them down in pencil a little**, that's it. So that they can be rewritten later.

119 **S01:** I really like this metaphor of writing them down in pencil a little.

..5.1. Essential Skill: 120
 ..2.1. European 121
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S00: Necessarily, yes, you know, the erasable ones and then I put them on top. But I must be flexible, I must continually review things. It is a cultural dimension called the **tolerance for uncertainty**. This cultural dimension, unfortunately, is scarce in human beings. And there are few people who have it. In Italy, in Europe, tolerance for uncertainty is low.

125 **S01:** Very interesting. So, let's say that, from a negotiation perspective,
 126 in this case, the adaptive part, the part that is more art than science,
 127 prevails more.

128 **S00:** There must be science in evolution, continuous evolution.

129 **S01:** Science in evolution, very beautiful.

130 **S00:** And then there is another aspect: this leads people to become much
 131 more distributive than integrative.

132 **S01:** Okay. Because uncertainty probably activates triggers related to
 133 amygdala processes.

..3.1.1. Challenges 134
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S00: It's certain, we are less rational, we don't care about the other side anymore. And so we focus only on ourselves. So this is a problem. Already, in general, negotiators are few. Those who will negotiate integratively, this probably leads them even more to be distributive.

138 **S01:** From this point of view, I ask you, because it seems to me to be one
 139 of the important challenges for negotiators. What, in your experience, is
 140 the most demanding negotiation you have participated in and observed?
 And
 141 what made it so?

3. Challenging Experie 142
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S00: I recently observed the acquisition of a division of a company from Bergamo. An Italian company, in the hands of the Germans, from Bergamo, which is now ending up in the hands of the Chinese. Because the Germans, due to their own headquarters problems, decided to sell it. And this acquisition was very complicated for various reasons. There is overlap in product and strategy, but the buying company has never made an acquisition before. Imagine, they have to go and buy one from Bergamo. And the company in Bergamo is full of Germans, plus the Bergamaschi. It is a historical company and, in my opinion, the negotiation is very complicated, especially

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if you then take it to integration afterward. **It will be very, very complicated because there are enormous language and cultural barriers.**

..3.1.1. Challenges

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Because this is not a company from Shanghai, it is a company from Southern China that speaks Cantonese, not even Mandarin. So it is very, very complicated. And it involved three players, because the German parent company, the Chinese, and the Italians were involved in the negotiation. It was not simple.

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S01: And what were the central variables that determined the success or failure of the agreement?

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S00: The success was determined by the fact that this company, among the various bidders, was the one that offered greater guarantees for the future.

..3.1.2. Outcome Deter

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In the sense that they have an hands-off approach, the management remained the same, so the Bergamaschi were very happy to be acquired by them. Because they are not imposing their management, at least for now. This was what was agreed in the pacts and as a first impression. It will probably be like this.

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S01: So the Italian side also played a role in the success.

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S00: They played a role in accepting who the buyer was. They negotiated with the parent company. Very interesting. Tripod (three-sided).

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S01: Very interesting aspect. Moving on to another topic that is linked to what we are doing here today, in the sense of the conference, one of the things that is obviously much discussed is the distance between the academic world and the world of practice. It seems to me that you are a bit of a master at this, in the sense of building a bridge between the two things, because you live in both worlds. And in your opinion, where do you see the widest gap?

..6.1. Research Questic

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S00: The widest gap can be seen very simply in the participants in the roleplay they do, from which negotiation theory is then derived. **They are all undergraduates.** Historically, this is the main problem. It is clear that it is simpler to have them in the classroom. However, this does not lead to a theory that is applicable in the real world, because those who negotiate have many more years, much more experience, they are not always better negotiators, but surely this is a huge problem. Because we create theory, in my opinion, from experiments based on participants who are not representative of the world of work. This is a huge problem. Second, the Academy lives a little in its own world.

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S01: This is always a good problem.

..4.1. Research / Practi

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S00: This conference already less so, but if you go to conferences in the United States, with film management and everything, **there are never any practitioners, there is never this connection.** And so the theory is the integrative one, which is not applied in everyday life. Why? Because there is no transparency. So it is very complicated.

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S01: You were talking about undergraduates, where you actually perceive the gap between the academic world and the abilities of those already in the working context. So is it a competence gap?

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..4.1. Research / Practi

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S00: The gap is that if I am a professor, I want to write a paper and I do it with a controlled experiment, my participants in the experiment are undergraduates. Okay. They are not real negotiators from companies. This is

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the big difference. I understand. And undergraduates do not have the experience, they don't know the condition of companies and often they don't

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know how to negotiate, because they are learning it there. **S01:** So, let's

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say that the data collection part is somewhat flawed. **S00:** It is not

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representative. It has a participation bias. Second, roleplays are used

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that are not always representative of the scenarios. It was said today and

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this morning, right? Representative of the scenarios that negotiators then

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face daily. because they are designed specifically to be calculated more

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easily, to have points and everything. Roleplays are not always suitable

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for simulations. But, certainly, the problem of undergraduates is huge.

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S01: How do you think this problem could be solved? Should we... Push academics less to produce papers and make them produce papers that make

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more sense. Because many papers that come out are absolutely useless.

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S01: Yes, just to create volume, because clearly there is that dynamic of academic distortion.

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..4.1. Research / Practi

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S01: And if you go read them, For those who negotiate daily they are absolutely useless. They are nice for the academy, but for those who... And this is also very important. **There is no one from the working world, corporate world, who reads academic papers.** Because they are not interesting to them.

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S01: Then, from my point of view, a distortion is created, whereby there might also be interesting ones.

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S01: //S00: But I don't go look at them, because they are immersed in everything else.//

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224 **S00:** But it becomes finding a needle in a haystack. And that has become a
225 problem. Instead, earlier you mentioned the United States, so I would ask
226 you if you believe the European point of view, therefore the European
227 context, always from the perspective of negotiation, is different.

..2.2. Non-European 228 **S00:** Yes, a difference exists because in the United States, negotiation is
229 taught a bit more. In general, it's a bit like public speaking, I make this
230 analogy. Americans know how to use it more than us Europeans. And also
231 negotiation, they know the difference between distributive and integrative
232 negotiation. In general. **Europeans much less so.** They rely much more on
233 experience, less from the classroom point of view, acquiring skills, and
..2.1. European 234 much more on learning in the role. And so it still leads to behaviors that
235 pass down from generation to generation. And this is evident. European
236 buyers have a very, very similar attitude among themselves and it is very
237 distributive, for example.

238 **S01:** In a certain way, a stratification of knowledge or absence of
239 knowledge is created. Exactly. So one continues to be distributive.
240 Negotiation continues between distributive parties. And consequently, one
241 continues to learn how to do it that way.

242 **S00:** You said it very well. It is a habit that propagates. So it is truly
243 the worst of the worst. Because there is no knowledge. We don't know that
244 integrative negotiation also exists. Can I trust him? Come on. It doesn't
245 exist.

246 **S01:** And in Europe in general, however, this too. This happened to me in
247 some classrooms, doing training, even with CEOs, they had a very
248 distributive approach and they passed this approach on to their employees
249 too.

250 **S00:** And it is their way of saying, look, this is how we do it.

251 **S01:** And it is a big problem, because then all their employees bore this
252 kind of imprint. And this also deviates them in their careers, because then
253 maybe they will move to another company, but they will bring that type of
254 approach.

..2.1. European 255 **S00:** Besides the culture of the courses, there is also the dynamic of two
256 very important industries. One is the large-scale retail trade (GDO). Think
257 about the weight GDO has in Italy, Germany, France, and they are very
258 distributive. Whether it's Carrefour or Aldi Esselunga. And the
259 metalworkers (engineering sector). Large companies, car companies, have
260 always negotiated very harshly. The Germans perhaps a little less, but
261 nevertheless, at different levels, it has always been like this.

262 **S01:** Let's speed up because in the chat, seeing how long we are going,
263 because it is a pleasure talking to you, so maybe we will postpone the
264 digressions until another time... I will go straight to the last questions.
265 First, I ask you, what do you think are the key competencies for

266 negotiators today and, in reality, also for tomorrow?

267 **S00:** The key competence, in my opinion, is that of... Actually no, let's do
268 the opposite. The biggest shortcoming that I see when running classes,
269 corporate training, is the ability to identify or create scenarios
270 regarding the interests of the other party and the alternative of the other
271 party. Truly absolute nothingness, very complicated, where there is
272 information asymmetry and people don't even commit to doing it and
dedicate
273 very little time to the other party. And when you say that negotiation is
274 between two people or between two parties, they say, "yes, I understand,
275 but I only have this information here". So this is really the foundation,
276 absolutely the foundation. Second, in the evolution, in my opinion, //
277 **there will be a huge gap between those who use artificial intelligence
and
278 those who don't use it.** That is certain.

279 **S01:** So if I asked you, what would be one tool that you would add as a tool
280 for negotiation?

281 **S00:** Absolutely that: **The ability to create effective prompts to prepare
282 for negotiation becomes fundamental.** Because otherwise, the gap
caused by
283 artificial intelligence is much greater than the gap in negotiation skills.
284 Or at least it accentuates them even further. **S01:** And, in your opinion,
285 what is one research question that you think scholars should ask
themselves
286 regarding negotiation?

287 **S00:** In my opinion, we take it for granted that integrative negotiation is
288 the best. It is. But in daily life, it is very difficult to get there. To
289 achieve transparency with the other side and all the rest. So, in my
290 opinion, we should take a step back and say okay, but granted that we want
291 to be integrative, can we better explain to people how to get there without
292 feeling exposed to the other party? Without transparency leading them to
be
293 exposed to the other party. And we should teach better, we should make
the
294 fruits of an integrative negotiation better perceived. If people haven't
295 perceived them yet. We all know that value is created and everything, but
296 what are the true benefits? This, in my opinion, we lose sight of a little.
297 Anyway, here AI will have a big impact. Because if AI really does provide
298 support that allows you to evaluate options alone, at that point, it is an
299 integrative negotiation. So maybe we bypass this research question.

300 **S01:** Oh, interesting. In practice, in a certain way, you manage to bring
301 the solution even before academia. Anticipating it. The last question is a
302 bit more... That is, if you had to choose a book and a film, related...

303 **S00:** I thought about it, yes, I thought about it. Because it was the only
304 question I looked at. So, book, and I thought about it, **Negotiation Genius,**

305 by Malotra. Of all of them, I'd say it's number one. Because it encompasses
306 everything. Both the theoretical negotiation part, making it a bit more
307 applicable, and the people part. Instead, the film ***Bridge of Spies***, do you
308 know it?

309 **S01:** Yes, I saw it, very beautiful.

310 **S00:** With Tom Hanks. The poor guy finds himself there making this
exchange
311 of... of prisoners, right? The Soviet, the American, how he acts is
312 interesting. And I like it very much. It's not usually mentioned, but well,
313 it's very, very good. Very good. Meanwhile,.

314 **S01:** I agree, regarding the film part. Book, of course. Who am I to say
315 otherwise? The film is certainly beautiful.

316 **S00:** I didn't know so many people knew it.

317 **S00:** S00: well, it is very beautiful. I mean, when they are on the bridge,
318 everything, beautiful, beautiful.

319 **S01:** All right. I thank you very much for your availability.

320 **S00:** //S00: Thank you, guys. A pleasure.

321 **S01:** .// Then we will keep you updated.

322 **S00:** Yes, we need to hear from each other anyway regarding our things.

323 **S01:** Very, very willingly. Very, very willingly. All right.

324 **S00:** //S00: Thank you, guys.

325 **S01:** Thank you. Thank you.